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DESIGN OF COOLING SYSTEM FOR TWO POWER TRANSISTOR MODULES

Abstract: In high-power applications, where a significant amount of heat is generated, heat sinks are essential to prevent thermal runaway and potential damage to the electronic components by efficiently transferring the heat away. Heat sinks are typically made of materials with high thermal conductivity, such as aluminum, with proper fin structures to increase the surface area for better heat dissipation. Adding fans increases the airflow over the heat sink, improving the heat dissipation rate. Manufacturers of heat sinks often provide recommendations or even bundled fan options specifically designed for their heat sinks. However, there are many more practical applications than the manufacturer's design notes cover, so additional engineering is often required to adapt the cooling system to the actual needs. A cooling system was designed and modeled using CAD software for heat removal in a power converter. The cooling system comprises two heat sinks, an axial fan, and a duct. The two transistor modules are mounted on each heat sink as a source of power dissipation. A prototype is manufactured according to the designed CAD model. The cooling system performance was first estimated through numerical simulation. An infrared camera was used to compare the simulation results with the results of the experimental measurements. The experimental results showed reasonable compliance with the simulation model.

Key words: Thermal management, Electronics cooling, CAD modeling, Air-cooling, Power converter.

1. INTRODUCTION

Semiconductor reliability and longevity are strongly influenced by operating temperatures; higher temperatures result in shorter lifespans. Therefore, effective thermal management plays a crucial role in enhancing the durability and reliability of electronic devices. This is particularly critical in high-power electronic converters, which generate substantial heat. Thermal management typically involves transferring this heat to the surrounding environment using various techniques, with the application of well-designed heat sinks being the most common approach.

Heat sinks, typically made of materials with high thermal conductivity like aluminum, are commonly used to draw heat away from high-power converters and dissipate it to the environment. Various heat sink configurations are available on the market. Still, it's important to note that these solutions may not always perfectly match the real needs, underscoring the task's complexity and challenge. Therefore, additional engineering is often necessary to adapt the heat sink to the specific requirements of the high-power converter.

Heat sinks absorb heat from high-power devices through conduction and release it into the surrounding environment through natural convection. However, relying solely on heat sinks often proves insufficient for adequately cooling high-power electronic devices. Forced convection is employed, utilizing air movers to accelerate heat transfer from the heat sinks to the environment.

Electronic circuits' growing complexity and power density have underscored the importance of simulation testing in prototyping. Initially, the electronic cooling system is meticulously designed and modeled using CAD software. Subsequently, the system's performance is simulated within a multi-physics software

environment under predefined conditions. If the simulation generates viable and promising outcomes, the practical construction of the device commences. A prototype is then fabricated based on the model, enabling further real-world testing and evaluation.

This paper presents the design, simulation, and experimental testing of a cooling system for two power transistor modules. The SOLIDWORKS 2023 CAD (Computer-aided Design) software [1] was used to model the cooling system and the SOLIDWORKS Flow Simulation package for CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) and thermal simulation. The simulation enables the determination of pressure drops, the influence of fluid pressure, flow rate, heat exchange, heating and cooling, forces due to fluid action, and many other parameters. Application of the SOLIDWORKS Flow Simulation module and simulation is beneficial for evaluating proposed design concepts, thoroughly developing products, solving emerging problems, and quickly realizing devices.

The paper is divided into following sections: Section 2 - the design of the cooling system is presented; Section 3 - simulation results are presented and discussed; Section 4 - experimental testing results are discussed and compared with the simulation results. In the conclusion, the key takeaways of the cooling system design were given.

2. COOLING SYSTEM DESIGN

Power transistors are crucial components employed in various applications, including power processing, DC and AC motor control, and uninterruptible power supplies. These devices generate substantial heat during operation, and if not effectively managed, elevated temperatures can result in device failure. The primary function of the cooling system is to efficiently dissipate

the generated heat, maintaining the temperature of the power transistors within safe operational limits.

2.1 Initial analysis

The cooling system design for two power transistor modules intended for an uninterruptible power supply is presented in this section. The power devices used in this study are FUJI 1DI200ZA-100, triple Darlington configuration transistors in the form of power transistor modules [2]. The most important parameter when conducting thermal analysis of any semiconductor device is the core junction temperature. Therefore, the core junction temperature is the indicator of a device's cooling system performance.

The project requirements for the operating current and voltage of the single power transistor module are $I_C = 37.5A$ and $V_{CE} = 10V$, respectively. Maintaining core junction temperature under a certain value while subjected to desired current I_C and voltage V_{CE} means that the cooling system should be capable of dissipating the total of $P_{DT} = 750W$ of heat ($P_{DT} = 2 \times 375W$). The core junction temperatures of the modules are to be kept under $130^\circ C$, allowing the safety margin of $\sim 20^\circ C$. The rest of the system design requirements that are to be obeyed:

- The designed system is to be exclusively air-cooled;
- Dimensions of the system not to exceed $900 \times 200 \times 150mm$ and mass of 6kg;
- Axial DC fans 24V are to be used.

Based on the dissipated power of a single transistor module $P_D = 375W$, maximal junction temperature $T_{jmax} = 130^\circ C$, ambient temperature $T_a = 30^\circ C$ and internal thermal resistance of the power transistor module $R_{jc} = 0.089^\circ C/W$ [2], the desired maximal thermal resistance of the single heat sink can be estimated [3]:

$$R_{hs} = (T_{jmax} - T_a) / P_D - R_{jc} = 0.178^\circ C/W \quad (1)$$

Considering previously stated dimension restrictions and estimated thermal resistance from Equation (1), two MULTICOMP PRO MP008476 [4] heat sinks are chosen, each for one of the two power transistor modules. The MP008476 heat sinks have thermal resistance $R_{hs} = 0.09^\circ C/W$ at the 5m/s of forced air-cooling. The fans chosen based on the forced air speed requirement (5m/s) and dimensions restriction are SUNON MEC0382V1-000U-A99 [5].

The initial system design analysis based on the requirements gave a rough idea of the possible cooling system performance. To gain more information, the cooling system performance has to be tested, first through simulation, followed by prototype construction and empirical testing if simulation testing gives feasible results. Also, the additional copper rail components, installed between power modules to ensure the proper functioning of the system, are adding to the complexity of the thermal analysis, and simple analysis done so far isn't sufficient to draw any definitive conclusions.

2.2 CAD modeling

Simulation testing of the fairly complex model presented so far requires an appropriate CAD model. In Table 1, the characteristics of the materials used in the construction of the cooling system CAD model are given, and they are also used in the simulation.

Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m-K)
Silicon	2330	124
PLCC	900	0.2
Al Alloy 6061	2700	200
Copper	8900	390

Table 1. Properties of the materials used for cooling system simulation. The aluminum used in the prototype is not anodized (eloxated)

As shown in Fig. 1 and 2, the prototype contains two heat sinks positioned facing each other top planes, two axial fans, an air duct to funnel the air from fans to heat sinks fins, and one fan that reduces the temperature of the copper rails connecting two power devices and heat sink surfaces.

Fig. 1. Assembly model of the designed cooling system

Fig. 2. Exploded view of the designed cooling system model: 1) heat sinks; 2) power modules; 3) air duct; 4) double fan configuration; 5) mounting plate; 6) copper rails.

3. SIMULATION RESULTS

Before committing to prototype manufacturing, the designed system was tested through simulation. The discretization of the reference equations was performed using a finite volume method and solved using an academic edition of the SOLIDWORKS Flow Simulation 2023. The ambient temperature condition is set to a room reference temperature of 27 °C. The amount of heat that one power transistor module releases while working is $P_D = 530W$ ($I_C = 53A$, $V_{CE} = 10V$). The computational mesh consists of 970,911 cells (fluid cells = 494,591; solid cells = 476,320). The coupled system of equations is solved iteratively. The dissipated power rating used in simulation and experimental tests is increased significantly, which pushes power modules into overload. This is done for the sake of experimentation, and it is not intended to be a working regime.

In Fig. 3, it is possible to observe the performed analysis and thermal simulation with two transistor modules and how the heat is distributed across the entire cooling system. The highest temperature of 85°C occurs in the vicinity of a heat sink and power transistor module contact, which can be assumed as a transistor case temperature (see also Table 2). The estimated junction temperature is, therefore, $T_j = 85^\circ C + 530W \times 0.089^\circ C/W = 132.7^\circ C$ for each power transistor module, according to Equation (1).

Fig. 3. Surface temperature of the cooling system components with numbered points of interest (see Table 2)

Fig. 4. Simulation result of velocity distribution at the cooling system outlet plane with numbered points of interest (see Table 3). Black rectangle at the top represents fan

4. EXPERIMENTAL TESTING

After the prototype was designed and simulated in the software, parts were purchased, and the heat sink was assembled according to the conceptual solution. The experimental setup of the cooling system prototype is shown in Fig. 5. The temperature distribution on the outer surfaces of the heat sinks and transistors was measured with a FLUKE DC300A camera (Fig. 6 and 7), and a K-type thermo-probe. The temperature distribution obtained from the simulation is in agreement with the experimental results (Table 2). There is a certain difference between simulation and experimental temperatures, which could be due to various reasons (neglected radiation effects, simplified fan model, omitted certain electrical elements from the simulation, like shunt resistors). The airflow at the cooling system outlet is close to the experimental results.

Fig. 5. Experimental setup of the designed cooling system

	Temperature (Simulation) [°C]	Temperature (Experiment) [°C]
1	31.93	36.5
2	37.26	35.8
3	39.75	33.8
4	49.05	34.2
5	74.87	67.0
6	79.44	64.0
7	73.85	65.8
8	85.26	81.3
9	75.04	68.0
10	67.92	54.5
11	44.89	46
12	30.42	39.2
13	75.61	66

Table 2. Simulation and experiment results comparison for heat sink surface temperatures.

	Airflow (Simulation) [m/s]	Airflow (Experiment) [m/s]
1	4.4	5.3
2	4.8	5.5
3	3.6	3.3
4	5.1	6.2
5	4.3	5.0

Table 3. Simulation and experiment results comparison for heat sink airflow.

Fig. 6. Thermal imaging at the connection between a transistor power module and a heat sink. Temperature reading at the red crosshair is 81.3 °C. This point roughly corresponds to the point 8 in Fig. 3

Fig. 7. Shunt resistors dissipate large amount of heat, hence the elevated temperature (134 °C) is visible on the thermal image

5. CONCLUSION

An initial analysis of the power electronics cooling system's performance can be done based on specifications given by heat sinks and fan manufacturers. Considering the complexity and specific nature of each application, further testing is required. Contemporary CAD software facilitates the experimental testing of complex electromechanical systems in the virtual environment with results very close to the empirical testing. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and Computer-aided design (CAD) are good tools for product cooling systems development with low cost and reasonable accuracy. In this paper, simulation and experimental verification of a concrete cooling system are presented. Both simulation and experimental results show the performance of the designed cooling system with power modules working at 140% of the nominal power load. Even when power devices are overloaded, the designed cooling system offers reasonable performance within design constraints.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] <https://www.solidworks.com>
- [2] FUJI ELECTRIC, "Power transistor module," 1DI200ZA-100 datasheet.
- [3] *Thermal Management: The Complete Guide*, CUI DEVICES. [E-book] Available: CUI DEVICES Resource Library.
- [4] Multicomp PRO, "Heat sink" MP008476 datasheet, Nov. 2021.
- [5] SUNON, "DC Brushless Fan & Blower", MEC0382V1-000U-A99 datasheet, July 2016.

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